

Mobile app analytics for assessing MOOC platforms: a study of online learners' sentiments

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Introduction

Massive open online courses (MOOCs) are the outcome of this improved internet connectivity, which get popularized very quickly among all the learners, and it also has paved the way among a wide range of communities, who have no access to the formal institutions, to get involved in online communities (Clarà and Barberà, 2013). A wide range of free courses in various disciplines are available through MOOC platforms including Study Webs of Active-Learning for Young Aspiring Minds (SWAYAM), Coursera, Udemy, FutureLearn, Class2Go and EdX for the people who intend to learn. Instant access of high-quality educational material regardless of any demographic or geographical barrier has attracted a large number of learners onto these courses (Balakrishnan and Coetzee, 2013). With wider and economic availability of mobile devices, MOOCs platforms are also offering their courses through mobile apps. SWAYAM and Coursera are also available on the Google Play Store as android-based mobile apps (Coursera is also available on iOS). The users are free to express their reviews about usage and functionality of apps on the app store in the form of star ratings or textual feedback. Often these app reviews remain untapped for evaluation and amendment purposes because of the lack of effective and simple technology, as a manual method to access it is quite time-consuming and tedious. In this study, the user reviews of Coursera and SWAYAM apps have been extracted and analysed by using the Web-based sentiment analysis (SA) tool AppFollow. Mobile app analytics involves measuring and analysing data generated by mobile platforms and properties, such as mobile sites and mobile applications.

Mobile App analytics is the measurement and analysis of data generated when users interact with your

mobile applications (AT Internet, 2019). The success of MOOCs has become possible through dynamic and self-organize engagement of learners where they share their skills, objectives, goals, knowledge and interest by commenting within the learning system using the social networking platforms (McAuley *et al.*, 2010).

The Indian Government has come up with its own indigenous MOOC platform SWAYAM. "SWAYAM is a programme initiated by Government of India and designed to achieve the three cardinal principles of Education Policy viz., access, equity, and quality. The objective of this effort is to take the best teaching-learning resources to all, including the most disadvantaged. It seeks to bridge the digital divide for students who have hitherto remained untouched by the digital revolution and have not been able to join the mainstream of the knowledge economy" (About SWAYAM, 2021).

Case study

This case study aims to investigate to what extent app developers can leverage crowdsourcing mechanisms for planning future changes based on learners' experiences. Specifically, opinion mining is conducted to compare SWAYAM and Coursera, a popular MOOC platform as mobile android apps. SWAYAM and Coursera apps have been evaluated using a SA tool "AppFollow" to know the user satisfaction of both apps. The reviews were collected from 3 October 2016 to 3 October 2021 for both SWAYAM and Coursera. To fulfil the objectives, the data of November 2021 is also included.

Google Play Store, for Android devices, allows users to rate the apps using star ratings and text reviews. The star ratings range on the scale of one to five. Free-text descriptions without having a predefined structure allow the users to freely express

their views to describe problems, issues and desired features. To assess, evaluate and compare the SWAYAM and Coursera m-apps, the SA technique is adopted. It is an advanced technology to analyse and perceive the behaviour of a user. Sentiments include feelings, opinions, emotions, likes/dislikes and good/bad. For analysing sentiments, unstructured textual data is processed to extract, classify and understand the feedback, opinions or meanings as expressed by the learners' community. SA aims to analyse and find the emotion or intent behind a piece of text or speech or any mode of communication, which may further be broadly categorized as positive, negative or neutral. The present study is done using the Web application AppFollow.

Learners' satisfaction towards SWAYAM m-app was viewed in terms of star ratings. Ratings are differentiated using different colours; 5 star (blue), 4 star (red), 3 star (yellow), 2 star (green) and 1 star (orange) as shown in graphics. The 5-star rating exceeds all the other ratings; 4-star rating is almost flat; 3-star, 2-star and 1-star ratings are almost overlapping each other. The 5-star trends keep fluctuating. It is attaining the peak in August 2019 and after that there is decline in user ratings.

The average rating of both the SWAYAM and Coursera apps is 4.2. The sentiment score that shows app's overall user satisfaction is 45% for both the apps. Its percentage is calculated based on the correlation between positive and negative reviews. The higher the score, the more positive the user sentiment is and vice versa.

Feedback metrics is an important feature of AppFollow that provides information about particular period. It gives an average rating of SWAYAM and Coursera of 4.20 and average rating by reviews is 3.75; total reviews of SWAYAM and Coursera are 11.1K and 25.7K, respectively; new reviews for both SWAYAM and Coursera are 595 and 706,

respectively. Updating of SWAYAM is 0.7% and Coursera is 0%; bugs of SWAYAM are 0% and Coursera are 31%. Reply given by the app developer of SWAYAM is 15% and Coursera 0%; the percentage of featured reviews that received replies for SWAYAM is 55% and Coursera is 17%; the percentage of negative reviews by users of SWAYAM is 35% and Coursera is 0%.

The following observations were made:

- The average total rating for SWAYAM and Coursera was found to be 4,195 and 4,206, respectively, in October 2021.
- The sentiment score for both the apps is 45%.
- The new version of SWAYAM 3.12.0 is available on 29 September 2021 with an average total rating of 4,202. During the period from 1 September 2021 to 30 September 2021, 75 reviews are received and 9 reviews are replied, whereas the new version of Coursera 3.2.3.0 is made available on 28 October 2021 with an average total rating of 4,190. During the period from 1 October 2021 to 31 October 2021, 157 reviews are received and 48 reviews are replied.
- SWAYAM and Coursera have 40,598 and 128,112 reviews worldwide, respectively, as on 9 November 2021.
- Total reviews for SWAYAM are 11.1 with a reply rate of 4.4% and total reviews for Coursera are 25.7K with a reply rate of 1.3%. For SWAYAM and Coursera both, during October 2021, the number of reviews and replies were decreasing. Both apps have very low/poor reply rates, and app developers need to respond to learners' reviews.
- The total number of ratings for SWAYAM is 40.5K out of which 4,418 are the positive ratings and 2,536 are negative ratings, and for Coursera, total number of ratings are 127.7K out of which 123,229 are positive ratings and 35,888 are negative ratings. The average rating for both apps is 4.2.
- For SWAYAM, 5-star ratings are 25.8K and 1-star ratings are 4.3K, and for Coursera, 5-star ratings are 81.5K and 1-star ratings are 12.4K in November 2021.

Conclusion

The growth of MOOCs is a big advancement and opportunity for online learners. MOOCs platforms are being widely used because of their potential to provide an online environment for learning at global level. In this study, a comparative analysis for SWAYAM and Coursera apps is done through AppFollow software to extract the data and to discover the emotions, feelings and sentiments of the users, and SA is applied to get the results. The reviews were collected from 3 October 2016 to 3 October 2021 for both SWAYAM and Coursera with the total number of ratings 40.5K for SWAYAM and 127.7K for Coursera. The results from this study are significant for the improvement and development of learning apps, to maintain and increase the user satisfaction.

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